

Pulp and Paper Properties of Jenitri Wood (*Elaeocarpus ganitrus*)

Dwiaji Agung Laksono

Departement of Forest Products Technology,
Faculty of Forestry Universitas Gadjah Mada, Sleman, 55281 Indonesia

Ganis Lukmandaru ✉

Departement of Forest Products Technology,
Faculty of Forestry Universitas Gadjah Mada, Sleman, 55281 Indonesia

ABSTRACT:

Jenitri trees are widely distributed in community forests on Java Island and their wood is utilized for various products. The objective of the study was to assess the basic properties and quality of pulp and paper from jenitri wood. The tree was felled at the age of 5, and the base part was taken. Chips were processed using three different pulping methods in soda (17% NaOH), kraft (17% NaOH and 25% sulfidity), and neutral sulfite semi-chemical (NSSC) (12% Na₂SO₃ and 3% Na₂CO₃) processes. The fibers of jenitri had good derived values (slenderness, Runkel, and flexibility ratios) as well as chemical properties. The screened yields from the soda, kraft, and NSSC processes were 35.60 ± 4.75%, 35.05 ± 3.83%, and 46.29 ± 2.59%, respectively. The kappa numbers from the soda, kraft, and NSSC processes were 28.02 ± 7.35, 21.15 ± 1.61, and 71.28 ± 6.86, respectively. The handsheets had a burst index value of 0.65–2.94 kPa.m²/g, a tear index value of 5.23–5.47 mN.m²/g, a tensile index value of 15.13–30.49 Nm/g, a brightness value of 24.39–45.25%, and an opacity value of 98.83–99.68%. The soda pulp and the kraft pulp had slight differences in all parameters except for the Kappa number. The NSSC pulp showed slight differences in the selectivity of delignification ratio, tear index, and opacity, but produced a higher brightness level compared to chemical pulpings. The values of burst and tear indices for kraft pulp paper met the Indonesian National Standard for leaf bleached kraft pulp.

Keywords: kraft, alkaline pulping, pulp wood, short-rotation, semi-chemical pulp.

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INTRODUCTION

Pulp and paper industries in Indonesia use 90% of the raw materials based on wood fiber. Currently, fast-growing *Acacia* and *Eucalyptus* species are utilized as main raw materials for pulping in Indonesia. However, due to high demands, alternative sources are needed to increase the production of domestic pulp per capita. There are some criteria to be satisfied for wood as a pulp material, including short rotation cycle, no specific environmental condition for growing, and good physical properties.

Jenitri (*Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb) is widely grown in community forests on Java Island. Its utilization is limited on its fruits and seeds. The seeds are commonly used as traditional jewelry, whereas the fruits are used as an anti-inflammatory [1]. Jenitri wood is rarely used as furniture due to its low specific gravity (0.40–0.45) and natural durability [2]. Jenitri trees have a rotation cycle of around 4 to 5 years and show a small heartwood portion at this age, which is an advantage for pulp production.

To the best of our knowledge, however, the pulping and papermaking potential of jenitri has yet to be investigated much. Various pulping processes can be applied to obtain semi-chemical pulp or chemical pulp from this wood. These include the soda, sulfate, sulfite, and neutral-sulphite processes. The sulfate or kraft process is the major process, but it negatively influences the environment because of the application of sulfur-containing reagents for lignin removal from plant materials [3]. Therefore, it is necessary to consume less chemical in the pulping process. The pulp and paper properties of different pulping methods have been addressed in previous reports [4,5]. In this study, the chemical composition, morphological properties, pulping properties, and physical properties of paper sheets from jenitri were investigated to evaluate the potential of jenitri wood in pulp and paper industries.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Preparation

Jenitri wood was provided from Peniron village, Kebumen regency, Central Java. An individual tree (5 years old, ± 17 cm in dbh, and 12 m in height) was cut and converted into wood chips ($3 \times 3 \times 0.3$ cm) and wood powder (40–60 mesh). There was no visible difference between sapwood and heartwood (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Cross Section of the Jenitri Tree

Specific Gravity and Morphological Analysis

The specific gravity (SG) of the wood specimens ($2 \times 2 \times 2$ cm) was calculated as oven-dry weight and wet-volume, alongside the density of water. Meanwhile, density was calculated as the ratio of oven-dry weight to conditioned volume as determined by the water displacement method.

The wood chips were disaggregated and macerated with a solution of acetic acid and hydrogen peroxide in the ratio of 1:20 for 1 h. A small amount of suspension for the preparation of a sample porter was made to be used on an image analyzer. The length, width, and diameter of light were determined by microscopy. The cell wall thickness of the fiber was mathematically determined as a half of the difference between the fiber length and the diameter of light. Lengths of wood fibres were measured with image-analysis software (Image-Pro Plus). The cell length of 100 fibers, macerated from small sticks with Franklin's solution, was measured by a digitizer (Olympus DP 70; Olympus Cooperation; Japan) coupled with a light microscope (Olympus BX 51; Olympus Cooperation; Japan). The cell morphologies of 100 randomly selected fibers were measured by image-processing software (Image-Pro Plus) according to IAWA[6].

The derived values were also determined for the Runkel ratio ($2 \times$ fiber cell wall thickness/lumen diameter), slenderness ratio (fiber length/fiber diameter), flexibility coefficient (fiber lumen diameter/fiber diameter), Luce's shape factor ($((\text{fiber diameter}^2 - \text{fiber lumen diameter}^2)/(\text{fiber diameter}^2 + \text{fiber lumen diameter}^2))$), and solids factor ($((\text{fiber diameter}^2 - \text{fiber lumen diameter}^2) \times \text{fiber length})$)[7,8].

Chemical Properties

The ethanol-toluene extractive [9], Klason lignin [10], and ash content [11] were determined for the wood powder samples. The holocellulose content was determined by the acid-chlorite method [12], and the α -cellulose content was measured after a 17.5% NaOH treatment [13]. The hemicellulose content was determined by the difference between the holocellulose content and the α -cellulose content.

Pulping Process

Air-dried chips equivalent to 300 g of oven-dried chips were cooked in an electrically heated rotary digester (KRK) with a capacity of 5 l for three replications. For the neutral sulfite semi-chemical (NSSC) process, pulp was made with 12% Na₂SO₃ and 3% Na₂CO₃ for a length of cooking time of 120 min at 170 °C with a liquor: wood ratio of 6.5:1. Fiber separation was carried out using a KRK refiner with a rotational speed of 3,000 rpm for 5 repetitions. Kraft and soda cooking processes were carried out with 17% active alkali and 25% sulfidity (kraft process) in the following conditions: a liquor:wood ratio of 4:1, a maximum temperature of 170 °C, a length of time to maximum temperature of 120 min, and a length of time at maximum temperature of 60 min.

After cooking, the chips were discharged and washed. The pulp materials were disintegrated and screened on a 100 mesh. The screened pulp was passed through a screw press to remove excess water, and then samples were taken for dry matter content and screened pulp yield determination. The screening rejects were collected and dried for calculating the total pulp yield. The Kappa number and viscosity of pulp was measured following SNI ISO 302-2014 [14] and SNI 8402:2017 (for chemical pulp) [15], respectively. The selectivity of delignification ratio was calculated by dividing the weight of dissolved lignin by the weight of dissolved carbohydrates during cooking [4]. The chemical properties of pulp were also measured by the same method for the wood mentioned above.

Handsheet Making and Physical Testing

The fibers were separated by a defibrator and beaten according to SNI ISO 5267-2-2010[16], using a Niagara beater, to obtain a freeness of 200–300 ml CSF. The production of 80 g/cm² of handsheets was in accordance with SNI ISO 5269-1 [17]. The mechanical properties of paper, such as the tear index, burst index, and tensile index, were measured respectively according to the standards SNI 14-0436-1989[18], SNI ISO 2758-2011 [19], and SNI 14-0437-1989-A [20]. Using the whiteness meter WSB-3, the optical properties of brightness and printing opacity of the paper were measured according to SNI ISO 2470-1-2014 [21] and ISO 2471-2008 [22], respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Basic Properties

Fiber morphological characteristics play a key role because of their influences on the quality of the production of paper pulp. For instance, fibre length has a direct effect on the tear index of *E. globulus* [23]. Furthermore, the derived values determined from dimensional measurements of the fibers contribute to the assessments of various properties of the paper. It is known that wood with higher values in fiber length, flexibility ratio, and slenderness ratio is expected to have increased mechanical strength for papermaking [8]. On the other hand, negative relationships between pulp strength properties and Runkel ratio, Luce's shape factor, and solid factor have also been observed [8, 24, 25]. The fiber dimensions and derived values of jenitri are summarized in Table 2. Obviously, the fibers of jenitri had good derived values (slenderness, Runkel, and flexibility ratios). Those values, in addition to fiber length and specific gravity, are comparable to the values of *Acacia mangium* grown in Indonesia [26]. However, the fibers of jenitri have higher solid factor and lower slenderness ratio than those of *Eucalyptus pellita* [27].

The chemical properties and behaviour of wood components during pulping are very important. High amounts of cellulose and hemicellulose are necessary as they may produce a high yield of pulp [28, 29]. The results of the chemical analyses of jenitri wood are presented in Table 3. The cellulose content of jenitri was found to be 45.2%, which is satisfactory. A low value of lignin content (21.27%) was found in jenitri, which suggests that this wood may require lower pulping time and chemical

charge compared to those required by *Acacia mangium* [30] and *Eucalyptus pellita* [27]. However, it was also found that jenitri contains great amounts of ash.

Table 1. Fiber Dimension, Derived Fiber Values, and Specific Gravity of Jenitri Wood

Physical properties	Jenitri	<i>Acacia mangium</i> ^a	<i>Eucalyptus pellita</i> ^b
Fiber length (μm)	960 ± 190	970-980	1020 ± 80
Lumen diameter (μm)	12.69 ± 3.02	14.48-15.08	6.94 ± 1.70
Cell wall thickness (μm)	3.45 ± 0.96	2.84-2.90	3.15 ± 0.52
Fiber diameter (μm)	19.59 ± 4.03	14.48-15.08	13.25 ± 1.64
Runkel ratio	0.56 ± 0.16	0.45-0.50	0.97 ± 0.30
Slenderness ratio	50.02 ± 9.50	56.03-66.98	78.21 ± 10.34
Flexibility ratio	64 ± 7	58-71	-
Luce's shape factor	0.41 ± 0.09	-	0.57 ± 0.10
Solid factor (×10 ³ μm ³)	228.94 ± 125.03	-	130.91 ± 33.77
Specific gravity	0.46 ± 0.04	0.41-0.50	-

Note: ^a [26]; ^b [27]

Table 2. Chemical Components of Jenitri Wood

Contents (%)	Jenitri	<i>Acacia mangium</i> ^a	<i>Eucalyptus pellita</i> ^b
Holocellulose	76.86 ± 1.65	77.7	75.26 ± 2.58
Alpha-cellulose	45.20 ± 2.20	46.5	49.02 ± 2.88
Hemicellulose	31.66 ± 3.84	-	-
Lignin	21.27 ± 1.22	27.3	29.49 ± 1.86
Ethanol-toluene extractive	3.04 ± 0.34	3.8	3.08 ± 1.00
Ash	0.88 ± 0.48	0.20	-

Note: ^a [30]; ^b [27]

Pulp Yield and Chemical Properties

Screened pulp yield could be considered to be dependent on unscreened (total) yield and rejects. In general, the results of NSSC pulping were higher than those of alkaline pulpings, with total yields mostly ranging from 57% to 60 % as opposed to screened yields, which were in the range from 43% to 49% (Fig. 2). Those ranges were still below the expected screened yield (75–85%) from NSSC pulping [31] due to higher rejects. A similar trend was also observed for alkaline pulpings. Normal soda and kraft pulp yields lie between 45% and 50% for hardwood. The pulp samples obtained with kraft pulping exhibited lower kappa numbers than those provided by soda pulping.

At almost identical chemical charges, *Acacia mangium* [26] and *Eucalyptus pellita* [32] produced kraft pulp with higher screened yields than that of jenitri. The results of kraft cooking indicated that jenitri was difficult to digest. Although the kappa number was fairly low (21.15), a substantial portion (11.47%) consisted of shives and coarse materials. A possible explanation is uncertain as the jenitri wood had a lower lignin content (21.27%). Therefore, these results of low pulp yields along with low Kappa numbers deserve a further analysis with an emphasis on extractive composition and lignin structure (S/G ratio)[33]. In addition, to achieve complete delignification, it is necessary to find the optimum chemical concentration in all processes.

The chemical composition of jenitri pulp is shown in Table 3. The lignin and hemicellulose contents and the solubility figures of the unbleached pulp were proportionately reduced in comparison to wood raw material. As expected, alkaline pulpings showed higher sugar contents and lower lignin contents than those of NSSC pulping. This indicates that the white liquor in alkaline pulpings delignified cell wall more intensely to give more sugar remaining in the cell wall. The kraft pulp showed a higher pulp viscosity value than that of the soda pulp, which indicates less degraded carbohydrate. The comparatively low lignin in the alkaline pulps might reduce the initial beating degree (573–580 ml) compared to the NSSC pulp (673 ml).

Figure 2. Pulp Yield and Kappa Number of Jenitri Wood (Average of Three Replications)

The kraft pulp gave a higher level of cellulose but lower amounts of lignin and hemicellulose compared to the soda pulp. During kraft pulping, hydrogen sulfide ions reacted with lignin, and carbohydrate degradation reactions were only affected by hydroxide ions [3]. α -cellulose does not experience any more reduction than hemicellulose because the glycoside bonds of hemicellulose are unstable and prone to hydrolyze with acids to become monomers containing glucose, mannose, galactose, xylose, and arabinose [3, 34].

The extractive contents of the alkaline pulps were higher than those of the NSSC pulp. This might be due to the combination of chemical and mechanical actions to intensify the extractive removal in NSSC pulping. However, the different processes did not exhibit any considerable differences in ash content. The ash contents in the jenitri pulp were relatively the same across methods. Malachowska [35] observed that the addition of active alkali from 20% to 38% did not affect the ash content of *Pinus sylvestris* wood even though the active alkali concentration was increased.

Table 2. Chemical Properties and Initial Beating Degree of the Jenitri Pulp (Average of Three Replications)

Components	Soda	Kraft	NSSC
Holocellulose (%)	91.88 ± 1.24	92.48 ± 0.83	87.79 ± 1.97
Alpha-cellulose (%)	77.19 ± 0.94	82.21 ± 2.76	62.34 ± 2.44
Hemicellulose (%)	14.70 ± 1.65	10.27 ± 2.05	25.45 ± 0.83
Lignin (%)	4.18 ± 1.10	2.00 ± 0.24	9.54 ± 1.03
Ethanol-toluene extractive (%)	1.90 ± 0.80	1.56 ± 0.76	0.61 ± 0.23
Ash (%)	0.72 ± 0.33	0.87 ± 0.29	0.80 ± 0.08
Viscosity (cP)	6.76 ± 0.18	19.41 ± 1.42	n.d
Initial beating degree (CSF, ml)	580.0 ± 10.0	573.33 ± 15.27	673.33 ± 11.54

Note: n.d. = not determined

The selectivity of delignification presented in Table 4 shows that the soda pulp and the kraft pulp had values that are not much different (0.56 and 0.58). The selectivity of the delignification ratio, which indicates the ratio of the weight of dissolved lignin to the weight of dissolved carbohydrates, is used to evaluate the cooking method [4, 36]. The comparatively low values of the kraft pulp and the soda pulp mean that the dissolved carbohydrates were still higher than the dissolved lignin during cooking. The lower or the closer to zero the selectivity of delignification ratio, the higher the loss of carbohydrates during pulping, and vice versa [34]. Low selectivity would result in a drop in the degree of polymerization and molecular weight of the cellulose polymer and in a reduction in the viscosity of the chemical pulp (Table 3). The low selectivity of delignification ratio of the soda pulp and the kraft pulp might be caused by the levels of active alkali used in this experiment. Biswas et al. [15] found that there was a decrease in the selectivity of delignification ratio when the active alkali increased

from 16% to 19% in the kraft pulping of *Anthocephalus chinensis* wood. An increase in active alkali concentration causes higher levels of degraded carbohydrates [37].

The NSSC pulp showed slightly different values in the selectivity of delignification ratio (0.55) than those of the chemical pulps. This indicates that the NSSC process did not provide any optimum results either because the carbohydrates dissolved during cooking were higher than the dissolved lignin. However, the NSSC pulp had lower amounts of lignin and dissolved carbohydrates than did the kraft pulp. This was caused by the low concentration of cooking agents used in the NSSC pulp [37].

Table 4. Delignification Selectivity of Pulp Jenitri Pulp (Average of Three Replications)

Measurement	Soda	Kraft	NSSC
Kappa number	28.02	21.15	71.28
Lignin removed (g)	59.08	60.20	48.95
Carbohydrates removed (g)	104.85	102.42	88.45
Lignin removed (%)	92.59	94.34	76.71
Lignin- free pulp yield (%)	35.90	36.72	41.38
Ratio of delignification selectivity	0.56	0.58	0.55

Physical Properties of Handsheet

Depending on the end use of the pulp, the strength properties of a pulp might also play a significant role in selection criteria. Various strength properties are presented in Fig. 3. Strength properties were determined after beating in a Niagara beater at 200–300 ml CSF. An appreciable difference exists in the process, in which case the strength properties of the kraft handsheets were higher than those of the soda and NSSC ones. Previously, the pulp samples of *Citrus sinensis* obtained with kraft pulping exhibited better yield, tensile strength, and tearing strength than those obtained with soda pulping [5]. The results indicated that lower kappa numbers produce pulps with better physical characteristics. However, the tear index from NSSC pulping showed higher values than those obtained from soda pulping. This suggests that although the chemical composition of the fiber wall is also important, another physical factor might affect the tear index.

Figure 3. Handsheet Mechanical Properties of Jenitri Pulp (Average of Three Replications)

NSSC pulp paper in terms of paper strength can be used as a raw material for wrapping paper [38]. The values of burst and tear indices for kraft pulp paper met the Indonesia National Standard [39]. The mechanical properties of jenitri wood handsheets from kraft pulping had lower values than those of *Acacia mangium* [26] and *Eucalyptus pellita* [32] from earlier studies. The physical strength of

paper is closely related to the fiber anatomy of the wood [7, 24, 40]. Luce's shape factor and solid factor negatively correlated to tensile index [24, 41]. The low physical strength of paper might be due to the lower fiber length and felting power values, as well as higher Runkel ratio and solid factor value, of jenitri wood compared to other species (Table 1).

With regard to chemical properties, the low strength of handsheets was probably due to the large amounts of hemicellulose components dissolved during cooking [42]. The carbohydrate content in the soda pulp was 14.27%, while the carbohydrate content in the kraft pulp was 10.27% (Table 4). The loss of hemicellulose might reach 50% of the initial content in the wood before pulping (25.67%). This also explains that high lignin degradation at a certain point will also reduce the strength of the paper because higher degraded lignin means a higher amount of active alkali used, which of course will also dissolve the hemicellulose in the wood [3]. Another explanation comes from intense cellulose depolymerization, as indicated by the low pulp viscosity value (Table 3).

The optical properties of opacity and brightness of jenitri handsheets from chemical pulpings were valued 99.52–99.68% and 24.31–28.81, respectively (Fig. 3). The NSSC pulp had the highest brightness level, whereas the soda pulp had the highest opacity level. The brightness of the kraft pulp was lower than that of *Acacia mangium* (35.56%) and *Eucalyptus pellita* pulps (34.05%) [32]. Opacity is a property that is related to the amount of light transmitted through the paper. The opacity of jenitri wood chemical pulp paper in this study had a value of 99.52–99.68%. The printing opacity value of the chemical pulp had met the standard for printing paper [43].

Figure 1. Handsheet Optical Properties of Jenitri Pulp (Average of Three Replications)

Technically, lignin oxidation that occurs during cooking also affects the color changes that occur in the paper. This oxidation process goes hand in hand with the process of lignin degradation, where the increase in concentration is followed by increased delignification and oxidation [44]. Furthermore, the increase in oxidation causes a darker color change in the paper. A low value indicates more intense lignin condensation in the kraft and soda processes even though the lignin content is low. The bright yellowish color in NSSC paper might be caused by chromophoric groups such as catechols, aromatic ketones, coniferaldehyde, stilbenes, and conjugated phenolics [45, 46].

CONCLUSIONS

The chemical and morphological analysis index values of jenitri are adequate for pulping and papermaking. In general, the strength properties of kraft handsheets are higher than those of soda and NSSC ones. The NSSC pulp has the highest brightness level, whereas the soda pulp has the highest opacity level. The values of burst and tear indices for kraft pulp paper meet the Indonesian National Standard for leaf bleached kraft pulp. The handsheets of the NSSC jenitri pulp have both adequate strengths and opacity needed for wrapping paper. The obtained pulp yield and kappa

number in this experiment indicate that jenitri is difficult to cook. Therefore, it is necessary to find the optimum chemical concentration in all processes.

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